

A Study on Buying Behaviour of Women Consumer towards Branded Cosmetics in Nagercoil Town

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Abstract

Today's women are going for brands which involves big name, trendy looks and style. The market is now dominated by brands which the people in the earlier days would not have thought of because of the prices and their mind set. Women are the most influential consumer group because they directly purchase or determine purchasing decisions.

This study attempts to analysis the the most preferred type of cosmetic and factors influencing to purchase cosmetics products in Nagercoil Town of Tamil Nadu. A total of 120 current customers using cosmetics were approached to collect data, by means of questionnaires. They were analyzed utilizing the descriptive research technique. The study found that the perceived level of brand reputation, advertising credibility, brand origin and experiential benefits of the cosmetic brand generates higher levels of satisfaction effects for women consumers. The results imply that marketers should focus on brand image attributes, quality and benefits in their effort to achieve customer satisfaction and loyalty. By maintaining and strengthening the brand images and values, it will position the brand positively in the minds of consumers.

Keywords: Women, Perception, Branded Cosmetics Product, and Buying Behaviour.

Introduction

In today's world, buying behavior of customers has entirely changed. They have technical knowledge about products, having alternatives, availability, emerging services from manufactured and ease of access. Women have an inherent love for beauty. The rapid economic growth, coupled with the huge development of cosmetics industry in contributes to the significant changes of cosmetics consumer behavior. Cosmetics have become a routine tool to make women more presentable. Understanding behaviour of consumers is a key to the success of business. As a huge potential consumer group, understanding of their attitudes and buying behavior towards cosmetics seems to be necessary. This study focused on investigating and analysing the purchasing patterns of women against traditional cosmetics. The limitation of the study is that it considers women customers from Nagai district only, and hence, might not be representative of the entire state. Successful brands live in the hearts and minds of the consumer. Brand consciousness is the new trend in

the consumer market. Today's women are going for brands which involves big name, trendy looks and style. The market is now dominated by brands which the people in the earlier days would not have thought of because of the prices and their mind set. Women are the most influential consumer group because they directly purchase or determine purchasing decisions for not less than 80 percent of all products sold. Women are multiple markets they buy for themselves, they buy for their families, in increasing numbers, and they buy for their business. She is the chief purchasing agent of the family.

Review of Literature

Keller (2003) the present study argued that famous brand names can disseminate product benefits and lead to higher recall of advertised benefits than non-famous brand names. There are many unfamiliar brand names and alternatives available in the market place. Consumers may prefer to trust major famous brand names for satisfying purposes. These prestigious brand names and their images attract consumers to purchase the brand and bring about repeat purchasing behaviour and reduce price related switching behaviours.

Khraim (2011) this study discussed that product quality plays a significant role in influencing consumers to be brand loyal customers. Additionally, the overall findings of the study showed that, amongst others, UAE consumers preferred brand name, product quality, price, promotion, store environment and service quality as relevant factors attributable to brand loyalty. All these factors showed positive relationships with brand loyalty, except design, which had no relationship. Undeniably, the cosmetics industry is one area which offers vast potential in the consumer market where there is an increase in social activities. More reliable and positive findings on this topic would have an impact on consumers, marketers and policy-makers. Marketers should find it useful to understand how loyalty factors can affect consumer-buying behaviour in the marketplace, which can help in segmenting consumers and markets for their brands and marketing communication. By examining how cosmetic usage determines brand perceptions, companies can improve their marketing strategies to enhance customer satisfaction and increase their customer base. Moreover, by identifying the brand personalities that attract consumers, companies can pinpoint the characteristics customers look for in a product, which in turn can be used to enhance brand image.

Objectives of the Study

1. To know the socio-economic profile of the cosmetics using consumers in the study area.
2. To find out the most preferred type of cosmetic and factors influencing to purchase.

Methodology and Research Design

“Research design is the arrangement of activities for the collection and analysis of the data in a manner that aims to combine relevance to the purpose with economy in procedure. The study carried out here is an Experimental Research.

The data that plan to be gathered for this research was obtained from both primary and secondary resources. The secondary sources of data will be derived from published articles from internet database, journals and magazines, theses, and related studies on cosmetics. On the other hand, the primary source of information regarding the study was collected by random sampling method through e-mailing and distributing the questionnaire prepared by the researcher, 130 people were surveyed.

The statistical data analysis was done mainly through descriptive statistics, using Chi-Square method. The SPSS software was used to execute the analysis process.

Analysis and Interpretation**Table 1 Brand Awareness of Respondents**

Awareness	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Yes	125	96
No	05	04
Total	130	100

Source: Primary Data

The table no.1 exhibits that in personal care products. Variety of brands has been introduced in the market in recent years against some few in years gone and each brand has numerous products for the beauty conscious women.

Table 2 Type of Cosmetic Applied

Type of Cosmetic	Frequency	Percentage
Traditional	10	08
Branded	120	92
Total	130	100

Source: Primary Data

The above table reveals that the traditional method of using the cosmetics like turmeric powder various flour etc has lost its value due to many reasons as explained by the consumers like time consuming, showing late result, tedious etc and therefore maximum 120 (92%) of the respondents are using branded cosmetic products for their good lookout of 130 respondents questioned.

Table 3 Monthly Income Levels of the Respondents

Income Category	Frequency	Percentage
Below Rs.15, 000	42	34
Rs.15, 001-Rs.25,000	38	32
Rs.25, 001-Rs.35,000	134	11
Rs.35, 000 & Above	12	10
No Income	15	13
Total	120	100%

Source: Primary Data

The above table shows the income level of the respondents majority of the consumers earn below Rs15,000 and between Rs 15, 001-Rs.25,000. Since maximum of the consumers here are employed and students engage themselves in part time jobs earning some amount for their studies as well as to purchase things for their use. Nearly 13% of respondents earn no income and dependent on their parents. Since the study area is a coastal region majority of the women employ themselves in sea food processing business for their source of revenue and to increase their standard of living.

Table 4 Factors Influencing to Purchase Cosmetics

Factors Influencing	Frequency	Percentage
Price, Discount & offers	56	46.7
Availability	8	6.7
Advertisement, Brand Image	22	18.3

Quality and Ingredients	21	17.5
Celebrity endorsement	02	1.7
Fragrance/Odor /Smell, Size/Weight	11	9.1
Total	120	100

Source: Primary Data

Table 4 depicts the factors which influence the women customers to purchase their beauty product. Maximum of them say that price being the prime factor followed by discounts and advertisement. Media plays a vital role in deciding the product purchase and its feature description. Manufactures must concentrate more on discounts and offering gifts to boost sales.

Table 5 Chi-Square Test: Association between Occupation and Purchase of Cosmetics

Occupation Status	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Sig.
Employed	40	33	0.001
House wives	23	19	
Agri and Allied	45	38	
Others	12	10	
Total	120	100	

Source: Primary Data

The above table explains that there exist a significant association between occupation status of the respondents and purchase of cosmetics among all respondents, since the chi-square value as revealed is 0.001 at 5% level. Hence it infers that a tough association between the two variables. There is a significance association between occupation status and purchase of cosmetics products in the study area of Nagercoil Town.

Summary and Conclusion

- Majority of the customers are well aware about the branded cosmetics products in the study area.
- It is captured that the influence the purchase of cosmetics products mainly depends upon the price of the branded cosmetics products
- Quality, brand and price are the main considerations for which women may switch from one brand to another brand
- It is identified that there is a significance association between occupation status and purchase of cosmetics products in the study area of Nagercoil Town

Every organization should be identified the taste and preference buying of products. Marketing research will go a long way in revealing the major demographic and other variables that have greater and stronger effects on brand preference for products. Therefore, there is a need to understand the important roles of each cosmetic product attribute i.e. price, quality, packaging, shelf life, fragrance, active ingredients used, and availability in order to enhance brand appeal. Thus it is high time that marketers and manufacturers realize, understand and recognize women as a lucrative segment and start developing concepts and create branded products that are women centric, which reap high growth potential. Price can be as a reason for women to turn them brand loyal. Quality of a beauty care product is the main feature which women consumer turns brand loyal. The high quality of the cosmetics helps to build the confidence of target customers and convince them to use

them. Customers tend to be concerned with the quality of make- up products before deciding to purchase them.

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